

The simultaneous non-aqueous potentiometric determination of binary mixture of pharmaceutically potent drugs

Vaishali R. Patil and Pradip P. Deohate*

Department of Chemistry, Shri Radhakisan Laxminarayan Toshniwal College of Science, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : pradip222091@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : The simultaneous non-aqueous potentiometric determination of binary mixture of pharmaceutically potent drugs by using isopropyl alcohol as the solvent and KOH in isopropyl alcohol as the titrant has been carried out. The two acidic drugs nimesulide-paracetamol and ibuprofen-paracetamol were determined simultaneously in their binary mixtures by non-aqueous differentiating potentiometric titrations. These drug combinations are widely used in medicines. The titrations were carried out using glass and calomel electrode pair. The method was found to be convenient for assay of double component tablets and results obtained are comparable with those obtained by I.P. method.

Keywords : Nimesulide-paracetamol, ibuprofen-paracetamol, non-aqueous, potentiometric determination.

Introduction

The potentiometric determination in non-aqueous media has been reported earlier using the different electrode pairs¹. Various methods have been suggested for the determination of two or more drugs in combination and deals mostly with the separation of components followed by estimation of individual component using suitable technique. The pharmacopoeias include methods for determination of drugs in combination². The literature is enriched with differentiating potentiometric titrations of mixtures like paracetamol-barbitone³, paracetamol-salicylamide⁴, paracetamol-aspirin⁵ etc. Determination of nimesulide-tizanidine⁶, nimesulide-chlorzoxazone⁷, nimesulide-diclofenac sodium⁸ etc. have also been reported in literature. Binary mixture of ibuprofen-paracetamol⁹ as well as ternary mixture of ibuprofen-paracetamol-chlorzoxazone¹⁰ has also been determined by spectrophotometric and chromatographic technique. Determination of combination of nimesulide-paracetamol and ibuprofen-paracetamol drugs by differentiating potentiometric method using acetone or isopropyl alcohol was not reported in literature so far. As these drugs are distinctly acidic, could not be titrated directly with aqueous alkali due to their hydrolysis. The basic titrant is also superior to the alkoxide solvents which are more susceptible to the atmospheric moisture and carbondioxide. The

present work is aimed at finding out simple analysis procedure for common drugs. This will help the analysis of raw materials and products for quick check of spurious drugs which are feared to penetrate the markets. In present study non-aqueous titrations were used to determine one component in presence of other without any prior separation. Determination of nimesulide and paracetamol as well as ibuprofen and paracetamol in two component tablets has been carried out using KOH in isopropyl alcohol as the titrant by potentiometric titrations.

Results and discussion

Simultaneous determination of drugs in double component tablets :

Ten tablets of the same batch containing nimesulide and paracetamol were accurately weighed and powdered. The required quantity of powder containing about 100 mg of each component was accurately weighed, it was extracted with isopropyl alcohol and the volume was made to 100 ml. An aliquot of 10 ml of this solution was diluted to 20 ml with isopropyl alcohol and titrated with KOH in isopropyl alcohol using potentiometer. Similarly, the powder of tablets of the same batch containing ibuprofen and paracetamol was extracted with isopropyl alcohol and titrated with KOH in isopropyl alcohol using potentiometer. The titrant was standardized by potentiometric

metric titration with standard benzoic acid in isopropyl alcohol. The weight of nimesulide and paracetamol as well as ibuprofen and paracetamol present in titrated amount of tablets was calculated. The same tablets were analyzed by I.P. method. The results obtained for two different brands of tablets are tabulated and it is observed that, the present potentiometric method gives fairly accurate and comparable results to those obtained by I.P. method (Tables 1 and 2). It is simple, precise and free from indicator error or interferences. The acidic drugs get hydrolyzed in presence of aqueous alkali but this is avoided in non-aqueous medium. However, in US Pharmacopoeia procedure alcoholic solution of the acidic drugs

is titrated with aqueous alkali. Such a titration must be performed quickly so as to minimize hydrolysis. The present method has no such limitations. Commonly the additives present in the tablets are calcium carbonate, sugars, gum etc. These additives are insoluble in isopropyl alcohol and do not affect the results. The solvent isopropyl alcohol can be used as a good differentiating solvent. The potentiometric breaks obtained using isopropyl alcohol are quite pronounced and prominent with minimum error (Graph 1). The solvent isopropyl alcohol permitted a large change in the solvated proton concentration near the end point. The dielectric constant of isopropyl alcohol is smaller one and it can be purified and

Table 1. Estimation of nimesulide-paracetamol in two component tablets

Sample	Label claim (mg)		Weight found by I.P. method (mg)		Weight found by present method (mg)	
	Nimesulide	Paracetamol	Nimesulide	Paracetamol	Nimesulide	Paracetamol
A	100.0	350.0	101.18	352.83	102.13	348.83
B	100.0	325.0	97.61	328.11	98.78	326.05

Table 2. Estimation of ibuprofen-paracetamol in two component tablets

Sample	Label claim (mg)		Weight found by I.P. method (mg)		Weight found by present method (mg)	
	Ibuprofen	Paracetamol	Ibuprofen	Paracetamol	Ibuprofen	Paracetamol
C	400.0	325.0	393.27	323.67	395.22	321.17
D	400.0	500.0	395.01	490.44	391.48	492.84

Graph 1. Estimation of nimesulide-paracetamol and ibuprofen-paracetamol in two component tablets.

made anhydrous very easily. This method is simple than the other methods in which the components are separated and estimated by chromatographic, spectrophotometric or other techniques.

Experimental

The potentiometric titrations were performed by a digital potentiometer (Equiptronics, EQ-602). Glass was used as an indicator electrode and calomel as a reference electrode. All weighing were made on Precisa-310-M (± 0.001 g) balance. The chemicals and solvents used were of AR grade. Solvents were purified and made anhydrous by standard methods¹¹. Care was taken to protect the titrant from atmospheric moisture and carbon dioxide. The drugs selected for present investigation was of pharmaceutical in nature and is included in pharmacopoeias². These were obtained from pharmaceutical laboratories.

Simultaneous determination of drugs in double component tablets :

In this analysis, ten tablets of the same batches of nimesulide-paracetamol and ibuprofen-paracetamol were accurately weighed and powdered. The powder containing about 100 mg of each component was accurately weighed and treated with 50 ml of isopropyl alcohol and stirred vigorously so as to dissolve the active component of the tablets. Binding agents or filler remained insoluble. The additives commonly present in the tablets are calcium carbonate, glucose, lactose, starch, gum etc. which are mostly insoluble in acetone and isopropyl alcohol. The solutions were filtered, residues were washed three to four times with small portions of isopropyl alcohol and volumes of solutions were made to 100 ml with isopropyl alcohol. The aliquots of 10 ml of these solutions were diluted to 20 ml with isopropyl alcohol and titrated with 0.1 M solution of KOH in isopropyl alcohol by potentiometric method using the glass and calomel electrodes. The titrant was standardized by potentiometric titration with 0.1 M benzoic acid in isopropyl alcohol. The end points were found out by plotting the graphs; the amount of drugs present in titrated weights of tablet powder was calculated. The amount of active components (drugs) present in one tablet was calculated by knowing the average weight of the tablet. Later on the same tablets were analyzed by the method of pharmacopoeias and the results obtained were compared.

Conclusion

The acidic pharmaceutical drugs selected for this study were nimesulide-paracetamol and ibuprofen-paracetamol. It could be noted that being distinctly acidic could not be titrated directly with aqueous alkali due to its easy hydrolysis but the non-aqueous titration of the drugs gave satisfactory results. The solvent isopropyl alcohol is found to be more satisfactory for the titrations. Potassium hydroxide in isopropyl alcohol was found to be better titrant. This basic titrant was also superior to the alkoxide solvents which are more susceptible to atmospheric moisture and carbondioxide. The calomel and glass electrode pair gave stable potentials which were quickly attained. In present research work, the simultaneous non-aqueous potentiometric determination of binary mixture of pharmaceutically potent drugs was carried out. It is fast, simple and precise which can be used even in common laboratories and do not involve use of any sophisticated instrument.

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